

Factors Influencing the Application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Data Preservation and Security in the 5th Industrial Revolution (5IR): A Study of Selected Federal and State Academic Libraries in Lagos

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Abstract

Purpose: This study investigates the factors influencing the adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for data preservation and security in selected academic libraries in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Methodology: Using a quantitative survey design, the research examines AI adoption levels, institutional readiness, and implementation challenges. A structured questionnaire was administered to 145 library staff across selected federal and state academic libraries. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations) were used to analyse demographic data and address research questions, while linear regression tested hypotheses at a 5% significance level.

Findings: results indicate that AI adoption for data preservation and security remains low, underscoring its nascent stage of implementation. Nevertheless, libraries showed moderate readiness to integrate AI solutions. Institutional readiness significantly influenced AI adoption, suggesting that preparedness is a key driver of successful implementation. The study concludes that to fully leverage AI's potential, libraries must enhance infrastructure, train personnel, formulate strategic policies, and secure consistent funding.

Conclusion/recommendations: It is recommended that dedicated budgetary allocations be established for AI-powered systems to ensure sustainable and effective digital preservation and security practices.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Data Preservation, Data Security, Academic Libraries, Institutional Readiness, AI Adoption, Nigeria

Introduction

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into library operations has transformed how libraries deliver services and manage information. Scholars such as Borgohain et al. (2024) and Okunlaya et al. (2022) emphasise that AI extends library capabilities beyond traditional human limitations, particularly by automating routine tasks and improving service efficiency. Innovation, therefore, remains a crucial driver of AI adoption in library systems (Li et al., 2022; Pan & Xue, 2023), offering improved information processing, advanced search capabilities, and enhanced user experiences. AI applications in libraries span diverse areas, including descriptive cataloguing, technical services, collection development, subject indexing, reference services, database searching, and document delivery (Asemi & Asemi, 2018). Tredinnick (2017) describes AI as a cluster of computational technologies designed to simulate rational decision-making in dynamic and uncertain environments. This shift enables academic libraries to increase operational efficiency, expand access to services both onsite and remotely, and boost engagement among staff and users (Ogar & Dushu, 2018; Pierce, 2022). Despite its benefits, AI integration in libraries presents challenges, including data privacy concerns, ethical implications, and the need for ongoing staff training (Wheatley & Hervieux, 2019; Farag et al., 2021). These challenges underscore the need for institutional readiness and strategic planning to ensure the

successful implementation and sustainable use of AI technologies. The ongoing evolution into the Fifth Industrial Revolution (5IR) further reinforces the importance of AI in reshaping library services.

The 5IR is characterised by the convergence of technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), robotics, virtual and augmented reality, cloud computing, and advanced data analytics—alongside AI, biotechnology, nanotechnology, and quantum computing (Ziatdinov et al., 2024; Noble et al., 2022). This technological interaction fosters innovation, personalisation, and data-driven decision-making, transforming libraries from passive knowledge repositories into proactive participants in the digital knowledge ecosystem (Enakrire & Oladokun, 2023). In this data-intensive era, data is both an asset and a vulnerability. As Sørensen and Lansing (2023) and Dou et al. (2023) note, AI and big data analytics play critical roles in extracting actionable insights, yet also raise significant concerns around data preservation and security. Libraries must, therefore, adopt robust data management strategies that ensure long-term preservation, resilience to technological obsolescence, and resistance to cyber threats (Ajani, Ahmed & Muhammed, 2024b). Moreover, librarians must adapt to these technological changes by developing competencies in data analytics, digital preservation, and information retrieval (Thirupathi, 2024; Bokho, 2023). Their role is central not only to safeguarding access but also to ensuring inclusivity, ethical governance, and sustainability in the digital library environment. Given this context, it is essential to assess how academic libraries, particularly in developing regions, are preparing to embrace AI for critical functions such as data preservation and security. This study, therefore, investigates the factors influencing the application of AI in data preservation and security in selected academic libraries in Lagos State, Nigeria. Specifically, it examines the levels of AI adoption, institutional readiness, and implementation challenges, contributing to a broader understanding of how libraries can navigate the complexities of technological transformation in the 5IR era.

Statement of Problem

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into library operations has become increasingly imperative, especially amid the rapid evolution of digital technologies. While academic libraries in developed countries are progressively leveraging AI to enhance service delivery, operational efficiency, and user engagement, adoption in many developing countries—particularly Nigeria—remains limited and inconsistent (Wheatley & Hervieux, 2019; Farag, Mahfouz & Alhajri, 2021). Existing research (Adeyemi, 2019; Ajani et al., 2022; Yusuf, 2022; Oyekale, 2023) indicates that a significant number of library professionals in Nigeria lack adequate awareness, skills, and exposure to AI applications. This deficiency not only hinders the modernisation of library services but also raises critical concerns about the capacity of Nigerian academic libraries to remain relevant and competitive in a globally digitised knowledge economy. The absence of strategic frameworks for AI adoption may perpetuate inefficiencies in information service delivery, widening the gap between libraries in Nigeria and their counterparts in more technologically advanced regions. As the global information landscape becomes increasingly AI-driven, there is an urgent need to assess the readiness, capabilities, and challenges of academic libraries in Nigeria to implement AI-based solutions. This study, therefore, investigates the adoption of artificial intelligence for data preservation and security in selected federal and state academic libraries in Lagos State. It aims to identify the barriers, opportunities, and institutional requirements for the sustainable and effective implementation of AI in academic library services.

Research Questions:

1. What is the current level of Artificial Intelligence (AI) adoption for data preservation and security in selected academic libraries in Lagos State?
2. To what extent are academic libraries in Lagos State institutionally prepared to implement AI-driven data preservation and security systems?

3. What are the major challenges limiting the effective adoption of AI for data preservation and security in these academic libraries?
4. Is there a statistically significant relationship between institutional readiness and the level of AI adoption for data preservation and security in academic libraries?

Hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship between the level of institutional readiness and the level of AI adoption for digital preservation and security in academic libraries in Lagos State.

Literature Reviews

Recent scholarship has increasingly explored the transformative potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in redefining library services, particularly in the context of the Fifth Industrial Revolution (5IR). Owraigbo, Abubakar, and Kanu (2025) examined how AI is reshaping the future of libraries and redefining librarians' professional roles. Their findings revealed that AI is shifting librarians' responsibilities from traditional information curatorship to more dynamic roles as digital navigators, data analysts, and trainers in AI literacy. The study identified essential skills for contemporary librarians, including proficiency in AI tools, data interpretation, and a strong understanding of the ethical considerations surrounding AI use. The authors concluded that AI can significantly enhance librarians' efficiency, broaden service offerings, and elevate their professional relevance. They recommended that library schools integrate AI-related training into their curricula and that libraries invest in continuous professional development. A key implication of the study is that the absence of AI tools and corresponding expertise may diminish librarians' effectiveness and reduce user satisfaction.

In a related contribution, Shahzad et al. (2024) conducted a systematic literature review to identify factors influencing AI adoption in libraries. Their study synthesised existing research and identified four major drivers of AI adoption: transformation of library services, the provision of innovative services, improved satisfaction for both librarians and users, and alignment with broader technological advancements. However, the review also highlighted several barriers to effective AI implementation, including technological challenges, lack of skills and knowledge, financial constraints, and organisational and cultural resistance. The study contributes a valuable evidence-based framework to guide libraries in adopting AI applications more effectively and efficiently. Enakrire, Oladokun, Nsirim, and Gaitanou (2024) explored the role of human-technology interaction in the 5IR and its implications for academic libraries. They argued that the collaboration between human intelligence and machine capabilities is central to solving both general and context-specific institutional challenges. Their findings pointed to the emergence of paperless libraries facilitated by mobile computing, cloud-based software, internet connectivity, and diversified electronic information retrieval systems. The study underscored the increasing prevalence of on-screen reading and the operational shift toward fully digital library environments. The authors concluded that encouraging human-machine collaboration is essential for fostering innovation, with paperless libraries serving as a model of this integration within the 5IR framework.

Ekwueme, Ajie, Ofodu, and Ambrose (2024) underscore the significance of 5IR technologies and examine their role in enhancing diversity and inclusivity in Open and Distance Learning (ODL) libraries. Their research shows that librarians view 5IR tools as crucial for enhancing data extraction, information processing, and service efficiency. Implementation strategies highlighted include raising awareness, curricular reform, professional training, institutional collaboration, and capacity-building. The study also stresses that dependable infrastructure- particularly funding and consistent power supply- is vital for sustainable adoption. The authors point out that human-machine collaboration can automate routine tasks and facilitate more personalised, inclusive services in academic libraries. Taken

together, these studies highlight both the opportunities and challenges presented by AI and 5IR technologies in academic library contexts. While the potential for transformation is considerable, effective implementation requires strategic investment in infrastructure, staff training, policy frameworks, and sustained institutional support. These insights underscore the importance of examining local contexts, such as academic libraries in Nigeria, to better understand the dynamics of AI adoption and to develop actionable pathways for successful integration.

Theoretical Framework

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis (1989) and later expanded by Davis, Bagozzi, and Warshaw (1989), provides the theoretical lens for this study. TAM explains how individuals accept and use new technologies, emphasising two key constructs: perceived usefulness (PU), the extent to which a person believes a system enhances performance, and perceived ease of use (PEOU), the degree to which using a system is free of effort. Together, these factors shape attitude toward usage (ATU), which influences behavioural intention to use (BIU) and ultimately determines actual system use. The robustness and adaptability of TAM have made it one of the most widely applied frameworks in technology adoption research across domains such as education, information management, and library services (Chuttur, 2009; Kurnia et al., 2016). The TAM model is specified below.

Fig 1: Technology Acceptance Model, source: Wikipedia

In academic libraries, TAM is particularly relevant for assessing the adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools for data preservation and security in the 5th Industrial Revolution (5IR). AI technologies promise enhanced efficiency, accuracy, and reliability in managing digital resources, but their success depends largely on users' perceptions and institutional readiness. For instance, when librarians and staff perceive AI tools as useful for improving data preservation and strengthening security, and as easy to use with minimal technical barriers, they are more likely to adopt and integrate them into daily practices.

Furthermore, TAM has been extended to include internal variables such as librarians' attitudes, pedagogical beliefs, and technological competence, as well as external variables such as organisational support, infrastructure, social influence, training, and demographic attributes (Asiri et al., 2021). In Nigerian academic libraries, these contextual factors are critical. Limited training opportunities, inadequate infrastructure, or a lack of organisational support may hinder perceived ease of use, thereby lowering adoption. Conversely, strong institutional backing and a positive professional attitude toward innovation can significantly boost AI integration for preservation and security. Thus, TAM provides a multidimensional framework for understanding the factors influencing the application of AI in academic libraries within the 5IR. By examining PU, PEOU, and their interplay with internal and

external variables, this study aims to identify the determinants shaping AI adoption in selected federal and state academic libraries in Lagos. This theoretical grounding enables a systematic analysis of both user perceptions and institutional readiness, offering insights into how AI can be effectively harnessed for sustainable data preservation and robust security.

Conceptual Framework:

The conceptual framework is adapted from the TAM model 1. Within the adapted TAM framework for this study, external variables are conceptualised as the combined influence of institutional readiness and the challenges hindering adoption. Institutional readiness refers to the extent to which academic libraries possess the infrastructure, financial resources, managerial support, and human capital required to implement AI technologies. It encompasses the availability of ICT facilities, adequate funding mechanisms, supportive policy frameworks, and staff competence in digital literacy. In contrast, challenges encompass contextual barriers that impede the smooth adoption of AI, such as high acquisition and maintenance costs, legal and ethical concerns regarding data privacy and intellectual property, organisational resistance to change, and the shortage of skilled technical personnel in libraries. These external variables shape librarians' perceptions of AI along two primary dimensions of TAM. First, they influence perceived ease of use: a well-prepared institution with robust infrastructure and trained staff fosters the perception that AI systems will be easy to learn and operate, whereas technical and organisational barriers create perceptions of difficulty. Second, they influence perceived usefulness, because libraries with strong institutional support are more likely to view AI as a valuable tool for enhancing digital preservation and security, whereas persistent challenges may lead to doubts about its relevance or benefits. Beyond shaping perceptions, external variables also directly influence the level of AI adoption in libraries. Institutional readiness can accelerate adoption, even when perceptions are still forming, by providing the resources and managerial will to enforce usage. Conversely, challenges can restrict adoption outright, regardless of whether librarians recognise AI as useful or easy to use. This direct pathway reflects the practical reality in academic libraries, where organisational conditions often determine whether adoption occurs, independent of individual attitudes or intentions.

The Fig 2: Adopted TAM model for the study

Research Methods:

This study used a survey to examine AI adoption, readiness, and challenges in Lagos State academic libraries. The population included 145 library staff, and a census approach ensured a 100% response rate, eliminating sampling error. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire that covered AI use, institutional readiness, and obstacles, as well as demographic items. A pilot study showed high reliability (Cronbach's Alpha 0.880–0.923). Data analysis involved descriptive statistics and linear regression at a 5% significance level to explore the link between readiness and AI adoption.

Demographic characteristics of participants:

The study surveyed 139 academic libraries, with 66.9% federal and 33.1% state institutions. Staff roles were dominated by Higher Library Officers (28.1%), followed by Senior Library Officers (15.8%) and Library Officers (10.1%). Assistant Librarians made up 9.4%, with Principal Library Officers and Librarians I and II each between 7.2% and 8.6%. Senior Librarians (6.5%) and Chief Library Officers (5.0%) held smaller shares. The data show mid-level staff dominate, with fewer senior managers and entry-level librarians. Females comprised 66.2%, males 33.8%, indicating a female-majority workforce. Age-wise, 31.7% were 51+ years, with significant numbers aged 41–45 (24.5%) and 46–50 (20.9%), emphasising experienced staff. Educationally, most held library science degrees: BLS/BLIS and MLS/MLIS, each 23%. Other qualifications included Diploma/ond (17.3%), Ba/b.sc (14.4%), PhD (9.4%), Ma/m.sc (5.0%), HND (4.3%), and M.Phil. (3.6%). Regarding experience, 30.9% served 16–20 years, followed by 18.7% with 11–15 years and 16.5% with 1–5 years, showing a mix of seasoned and early-career staff.

Results:

This study investigated the factors influencing the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in data preservation and security within the context of the Fifth Industrial Revolution (5IR), focusing on selected federal and state academic libraries in Lagos, Nigeria. This chapter presents the results of the data analyses conducted to address the research questions and test the study hypotheses.

Research Question 1: What is the current level of Artificial Intelligence (AI) adoption for data preservation and security in selected academic libraries in Lagos State?

Table 1: Level of application of AI for data preservation of library resources (N = 139)

Level of AI application for data preservation	Very High (4)	High (3)	Low (2)	Very Low (1)	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev
AI improves the accuracy of detecting damaged or corrupted files for preservation.	17 (12.2%)	53 (38.1%)	29 (20.9%)	40 (28.8%)	2.34	1.02
AI systems help automate digital file management	13 (9.4%)	48 (34.5%)	41 (29.5%)	37 (26.6%)	2.27	0.96
your library's use of AI has improved long-term accessibility of digital resources.	10 (7.2%)	50 (36.0%)	43 (30.9%)	36 (25.9%)	2.24	0.92
Your library actively applies AI technologies in data preservation practices.	12 (8.6%)	36 (25.9%)	43 (30.9%)	48 (34.5%)	2.09	0.97
library uses AI-powered backup solutions.	12 (8.6%)	30 (21.6%)	51 (36.7%)	46 (33.1%)	2.06	0.95
Overall Mean = 2.20						

Source: Authors computation (2025).

Decision Rule: If the mean is 1.0 - 1.74 = Very Low; 1.75 to 2.49 = Low; 2.50 to 3.24 = High; 3.25 to 4 = Very High.

The findings indicate that the overall level of Artificial Intelligence (AI) application in data preservation across the selected academic libraries in Lagos State is low, with an overall mean score of 2.20. This suggests that AI adoption for data preservation in these libraries is generally limited. Among the specific aspects evaluated, the highest mean score of 2.34 was recorded for the item stating that AI improves the accuracy of detecting damaged or corrupted files for preservation. Even so, this score still falls within the low-usage category. Similarly, AI systems supporting the automation of digital file

management recorded a mean score of 2.27, while AI-powered backup solutions had the lowest mean score of 2.06, indicating minimal deployment in this domain. These results imply that, although there is some awareness and limited application of AI technologies for functions such as damage detection and digital file management, the overall integration of AI into data preservation practices remains inadequate in the sampled academic libraries.

Table 2: Level of application of AI for data security of library resources (N = 139)

Level of AI application for data security	Very High (4)	High (3)	Low (2)	Very Low (1)	Mean (\bar{x})	Std Dev
AI systems help automate data integrity checks.	15 (10.8%)	45 (32.4%)	37 (26.6%)	42 (30.2%)	2.24	1.004
AI tools are used to monitor digital resources in my library	9 (6.5%)	35 (25.2%)	50 (36.0%)	45 (32.4%)	2.06	0.915
AI helps to detect threats in your digital preservation systems.	8 (5.8%)	42 (30.2%)	36 (25.9%)	53 (38.1%)	2.04	0.959
AI helps to prevent data loss in your digital preservation systems.	5 (3.6%)	41 (29.5%)	46 (33.1%)	47 (33.8%)	2.03	0.884
AI tools are used to secure digital resources in my library	8 (5.8%)	30 (21.6%)	55 (39.6%)	46 (33.1%)	2.00	0.885
Overall Mean = 2.07						

Source: Author's computation (2025).

Decision Rule: If the mean is 1.0 - 1.74 = Very Low; 1.75 to 2.49 = Low; 2.50 to 3.24 = High; 3.25 to 4 = Very High.

Table 2 presents findings on the level of AI application in data security across the selected academic libraries, with an overall mean of 2.07. This suggests that AI solutions for securing digital resources have not been widely implemented in these libraries. Among the individual indicators, the highest mean score of 2.24 was reported for the statement that AI systems help automate data integrity checks; however, this still falls within the low application category. Other items, such as the use of AI tools to monitor digital resources (mean = 2.06) and AI-assisted threat detection in digital preservation systems (mean = 2.04), also show low adoption. The lowest mean score of 2.00 was recorded for the item, indicating that AI tools are used to secure digital resources in the respondents' libraries. These findings highlight a significant gap in the adoption of AI-driven security measures, underscoring the need for greater integration of AI technologies to enhance the security of digital resources in academic libraries.

Research Question 2: To what extent are academic libraries in Lagos State institutionally prepared to implement AI-driven data preservation and security systems?

Table 3: Institutional Readiness for AI-Powered Preservation of library resources (N = 139)

Items	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Agree (1)	Mean (\bar{x})	Std Dev
Library staff possess the necessary technical expertise to operate AI preservation tools effectively.	8 (5.8%)	60 (43.2%)	54 (38.8%)	17 (12.2%)	2.42	0.78
My library has sufficient technological infrastructure to support AI-powered data preservation	15 (10.8%)	45 (32.4%)	57 (41.0%)	22 (15.8%)	2.38	0.88
My institution has formal policies and guidelines	10 (7.2%)	54 (38.8%)	47 (33.8%)	28 (20.1%)	2.33	0.88

supporting AI integration for data preservation.						
Our institution provides ongoing professional development to enhance staff competence in AI-powered digital preservation.	13 (9.4%)	44 (31.7%)	54 (38.8%)	28 (20.1%)	2.30	0.90
There is consistent staff training available for AI-powered digital preservation tools.	11 (7.9%)	44 (31.7%)	55 (39.6%)	29 (20.9%)	2.27	0.88
The institution allocates adequate funding for AI adoption in digital preservation activities.	4 (2.9%)	39 (28.1%)	69 (49.6%)	27 (19.4%)	2.14	0.76

Overall Mean = 2.31

Source: Author's computation (2025).

Decision Rule: If the mean is 1.0 - 1.74 = Strongly Disagree; 1.75 to 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50 to 3.24 = Agree; 3.25 to 4 = Strongly Agree.

The institutional readiness of Lagos State academic libraries for AI-driven data preservation is low, with a mean score of 2.38. Staff technical expertise scored highest at 2.42, indicating some foundational skills but not enough for full AI implementation. Infrastructure support closely followed at 2.38, showing partial capacity. Funding was the weakest at 2.14, underscoring financial constraints. Policies (2.33), training (2.27- 2.30), and human capital development are insufficient. Despite some readiness, major gaps in funding, policies, and staff development hinder effective AI integration.

Table 4: Institutional Readiness for AI-Powered Security of library resources (N = 139)

Item	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Agree (1)	Mean (\bar{x})	Std Dev
Library staff possess the necessary technical expertise to operate AI security tools effectively.	14 (10.1)	57 (41.0)	48 (34.5)	20 (14.4)	2.47	0.86
My institution has formal policies and guidelines supporting AI integration for data security.	13 (9.4%)	44 (31.7%)	65 (46.8%)	17 (12.2%)	2.38	0.82
Management demonstrates commitment to implementing AI in data security operations	7 (5.0%)	52 (37.4%)	58 (41.7%)	22 (15.8%)	2.32	0.80
My library has sufficient technological infrastructure to support AI-powered data security systems	9 (6.5%)	45 (32.4%)	61 (43.9%)	24 (17.3%)	2.28	0.83
There is consistent staff training available for AI-powered data security tools.	13 (9.4%)	38 (27.3%)	59 (42.4%)	29 (20.9%)	2.25	0.89
The institution allocates adequate funding for AI adoption in data security	10 (7.2%)	37 (26.6%)	66 (47.5%)	26 (18.7%)	2.22	0.83

Overall Mean = 2.32

Source: Author's computation (2025).

Decision Rule: If the mean is 1.0 - 1.74 = Strongly Disagree; 1.75 to 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50 to 3.24 = Agree; 3.25 to 4 = Strongly Agree.

The findings in Table 4 indicate that the institutional readiness of academic libraries in Lagos State to implement AI-driven data security systems is low, with an overall mean of 2.32. Among the readiness indicators, staff with the technical expertise to operate AI security tools recorded the highest mean of 2.47, indicating that while some competency exists among library personnel, it remains insufficient to ensure strong readiness. This was followed by formal policies and guidelines supporting AI integration (mean = 2.38) and management commitment to AI security implementation (mean = 2.32). However, significant deficiencies were identified in technological infrastructure (mean = 2.28), staff training (mean = 2.25), and funding allocation (mean = 2.22). These low scores indicate inadequate support for the sustainable adoption of AI in data security operations. Overall, these results suggest that academic libraries in Lagos State currently lack the essential infrastructure, training programs, and financial commitment necessary for the effective implementation of AI-powered data security systems.

Research Question 3: What are the major challenges limiting the effective adoption of AI for data preservation and security in these academic libraries?

Table 5: Challenges facing AI-Powered Preservation of library resources (N = 139)

Item	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Agree (1)	Mean (\bar{x})	Std Dev
High costs of AI technologies limit implementation efforts in digital preservation.	41 (29.5%)	58 (41.7%)	25 (18.0%)	15 (10.8%)	2.90	0.95
A lack of technical expertise remains a major obstacle to AI adoption in digital preservation.	36 (25.9%)	52 (37.4%)	36 (25.9%)	15 (10.8%)	2.78	0.95
Limited access to appropriate AI tools suitable for digital preservation is a challenge.	28 (20.1%)	64 (46.0%)	32 (23.0%)	15 (10.8%)	2.76	0.90
The absence of clear national or institutional policies delays AI implementation for digital preservation.	25 (18.0%)	62 (44.6%)	37 (26.6%)	15 (10.8%)	2.70	0.89
Ethical concerns, such as algorithmic bias, discourage AI applications in digital preservation.	19 (13.7%)	71 (51.1%)	29 (20.9%)	20 (14.4%)	2.64	0.89
Overall Mean = 2.76						

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

Decision Rule: If the mean is 1.0 - 1.74 = Strongly Disagree; 1.75 to 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50 to 3.24 = Agree; 3.25 to 4 = Strongly Agree.

The findings show that academic libraries in Lagos State generally agree that several barriers hinder AI adoption for data preservation, with an overall mean score of 2.76. The top challenge is high AI technology costs (mean = 2.90), highlighting financial limitations. This is followed by a lack of technical expertise among staff (mean = 2.78), which impedes effective use of AI. Limited access to suitable AI tools (mean = 2.76) and the absence of clear policies (mean = 2.70) are also significant barriers. Ethical concerns, such as algorithmic bias (mean = 2.64), are less prominent. These results suggest that resource constraints and skill gaps are the primary obstacles to AI adoption, despite the acknowledgement of ethical issues.

Table 6: Challenges facing AI-Powered Security of library resources (N = 139)

Item	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Agree (1)	Mean (\bar{x})	Std Dev
High costs of AI technologies limit implementation efforts in digital security	35 (25.2%)	56 (40.3%)	35 (25.2%)	13 (9.4%)	2.81	0.92
Lack of technical expertise remains a major obstacle to AI adoption for digital security.	36 (25.9%)	52 (37.4%)	34 (24.5%)	17 (12.2%)	2.77	0.97
The absence of clear national or institutional policies delays AI implementation for digital security.	27 (19.4%)	60 (43.2%)	37 (26.6%)	15 (10.8%)	2.71	0.90
Limited access to appropriate AI tools suitable for digital security is a challenge.	19 (13.7%)	70 (50.4%)	37 (26.6%)	13 (9.4%)	2.68	0.83
Ethical concerns such as data privacy discourage AI application in digital security.	23 (16.5%)	59 (42.4%)	42 (30.2%)	15 (10.8%)	2.65	0.88
Overall Mean = 2.32						

Source: Authors computation (2025).

Decision Rule: If the mean is 1.0 - 1.74 = Strongly Disagree; 1.75 to 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50 to 3.24 = Agree; 3.25 to 4 = Strongly Agree.

The analysis of challenges to implementing AI-powered data security in academic libraries in Lagos State shows general agreement among respondents that several barriers impede effective adoption, with an overall mean score of 2.32. The most critical barrier is the high cost of AI technologies (mean = 2.81), indicating that financial constraints are the primary obstacle to adopting AI for digital security. Closely following is the lack of technical expertise among staff (mean = 2.77), highlighting significant skill gaps that hinder successful implementation. Additionally, the absence of clear institutional policies and guidelines (mean = 2.71) and limited access to appropriate AI tools (mean = 2.68) further exacerbate challenges in deploying secure AI systems. Ethical concerns, particularly those related to data privacy (mean = 2.65), were also acknowledged but ranked slightly lower, suggesting that while ethical considerations remain relevant, financial and technical challenges are more immediate and pressing issues for these academic libraries.

Hypotheses

Four hypotheses were formulated and tested using a linear regression model to examine the relationship between the frequency of AI utilisation and library service quality among users of the UNILAG main library.

Hypothesis 1: Hypothesis: There is no significant influence of AI readiness on AI adoption for digital preservation of library resources in academic libraries in Lagos state.

Table 7. Influence of institutional readiness on AI adoption for digital preservation of library resources

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	T	P	R ²
(Constant)	.475	.181		2.622	.010	0.425
Institutional Readiness	.752	.075	.652	10.069	.000	

Dependent Variable: Adoption of AI-powered preservation. F (1, 137) = 101.391, $p < 0.05$. T (DF = 137)

Source: Researcher's Field Survey 2025, Note: significant at 0.05.

The results presented in Table 7 indicate a significant positive influence of institutional readiness on the adoption of AI for digital preservation in academic libraries in Lagos State (F(1,137) = 101.391, $p < 0.05$, $R^2 = 0.425$). The regression model accounts for 42.5% of the variance in AI adoption for digital

preservation. The unstandardized coefficient ($B = 0.752$) suggests that a one-unit increase in institutional readiness corresponds to a 0.752 increase in the AI adoption score. Furthermore, the standardised Beta value of 0.652 indicates a strong positive correlation between institutional readiness and AI adoption for digital preservation of library resources. These findings lead to rejection of the null hypothesis, confirming that institutional readiness significantly influences AI adoption for digital preservation in the sampled academic libraries.

Hypothesis 2: Hypothesis: There is no significant influence of AI readiness on AI adoption for digital security of library resources in academic libraries in Lagos state.

Table 7. Influence of frequency of institutional readiness on AI adoption for digital security of library resources

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	T	P	R ²
(Constant)	.570	.198		2.879	.005	
Institutional Readiness	.647	.082	.561	7.930	.000	0.315

Dependent Variable: Adoption of AI-powered security. $F(1, 137) = 62.844, p < 0.05$. $T(DF = 137)$

Source: Researcher's Field Survey 2025, Note: significant at 0.05.

This hypothesis tested whether institutional readiness has no significant influence on the adoption of AI for the digital security of library resources in academic libraries in Lagos State. Results from the regression analysis (Table 7) indicate that institutional readiness exerts a significant positive effect on AI adoption for digital security, $F(1, 137) = 62.884, p < 0.05$. The model explains 31.5% of the variance in AI adoption for digital security ($R^2 = 0.315$). The unstandardized coefficient ($B = 0.647$) indicates that a one-unit increase in institutional readiness is associated with a 0.647 increase in AI adoption scores for digital security. Additionally, the standardised Beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.561$) demonstrates a significant positive correlation between institutional readiness and AI adoption for the digital security of library resources. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that institutional readiness is a significant predictor of AI adoption for digital security in academic libraries.

Discussion of findings:

The adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Library and Information Science (LIS) remains low in many developing countries, particularly Nigeria, despite its demonstrated potential benefits. While awareness of AI capabilities is increasing among librarians, the actual implementation and integration into library services continue to lag. Several studies have attributed this low adoption rate to multiple factors, including infrastructural deficits, high costs, and concerns over job displacement (Odeyemi, 2019; Ajani et al., 2022; Yusuf et al., 2022; Oyekale, 2023). These challenges raise significant concerns about the feasibility of fully implementing AI in academic libraries to align with global trends and maintain competitive advantages in information access and service delivery. Supporting these findings, Mbagwu (2025) reported similarly low levels of AI adoption among academic librarians across three higher education institutions in Imo State, where AI tools were largely unavailable for library service delivery. Amuta (2021) and Okafor and Adebayo (2019) further identified poor internet connectivity, unreliable power supply, and limited access to modern computer hardware as prevalent obstacles hindering AI adoption in Nigerian libraries. Complementing these observations, Orubebe, Oloniruba, and Oladokun (2024) highlighted a combination of barriers—including high costs, lack of technical expertise, inadequate infrastructure, and resistance to change—as contributing factors to the slow uptake of AI in library services. Okafor and Adebayo (2019) also emphasised limited funding and the urgent need for specialised skills among library staff, despite growing interest and increasing

deployment of AI tools (Amuta, 2021). The full integration of digital resources into library services is pivotal for promoting information literacy and encouraging greater engagement with library materials, particularly in the context of online learning (Adetoro & Olatokun, 2020; Oladejo, 2019). Professional development programs in digital librarianship are essential for equipping library personnel with the skills needed to meet the demands of contemporary library services. It is noteworthy that many library staff members have been trained predominantly in traditional practices, underscoring the urgent need for training programs that develop competencies in AI, machine learning, and data science (Adebayo & Aina, 2019). Without such capacity building, libraries may struggle to harness AI's full potential. Akhimien and Osawele (2025) underscore the benefits of AI in research assistance, highlighting its capacity to enhance academic endeavours by efficiently searching databases and summarising relevant literature. However, the implementation of AI also demands careful attention to data privacy and ethical concerns. This overview highlights AI's transformative potential for library services while emphasising the necessity for responsible application to maximise benefits. Policy recommendations include the need for collaboration between government agencies and library management to chart a strategic path forward for academic libraries, ensuring alignment with global AI adoption standards. Continuous training and retraining of library staff in AI applications are imperative to enhance service delivery. Giwa et al. (2024) and Adebayo (2020) observe that Nigerian libraries employing AI technologies represent a fresh impetus toward the development of intelligent libraries, with several universities making notable progress in digitising their resources. The adoption of AI in Nigerian academic libraries is largely driven by the quest for more efficient information management, improved user experience, and enhanced support for research activities. In response to global trends, librarians have begun implementing AI technologies in specialised library sections. Innovative AI applications in library operations include the use of robotics and expert systems to support functions such as acquisitions, cataloguing, classification, and reference services. Applying AI to library services effectively automates complex, labour-intensive tasks, thereby reducing the likelihood of human error and improving the accuracy of information processing. AI facilitates seamless access to research materials, enabling faster and more efficient retrieval of relevant information. Moreover, AI helps mitigate challenges associated with limited human engagement by providing personalised assistance and support through automated systems such as virtual reference services and intelligent search tools. This not only enhances the user experience but also allows library staff to focus on higher-level strategic functions, ultimately improving overall service delivery and operational efficiency within academic libraries.

Conclusion

This study examined the adoption, readiness, and challenges associated with the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for data preservation and security in selected academic libraries in Lagos State, Nigeria. The findings indicate that although AI has the potential to enhance the accuracy, efficiency, and effectiveness of preservation and security operations within libraries, its current level of application remains generally low. This suggests that AI adoption in these academic libraries remains at an early, suboptimal stage. Regarding institutional readiness, the results reveal a moderate level of preparedness among the academic libraries studied, characterised by some technical expertise, partial availability of technological infrastructure, and limited policy frameworks. However, significant gaps persist in areas such as continuous staff training, formalised guidelines, and adequate funding. These deficiencies pose considerable obstacles to the full-scale implementation of AI solutions. The study further identified key barriers impeding AI adoption, notably the high cost of AI technologies, insufficient technical expertise, limited access to appropriate AI tools, the absence of comprehensive institutional policies, and ethical concerns. These challenges collectively hinder the effective integration of AI into library operations. Hypothesis testing demonstrated that institutional readiness significantly influences AI adoption for

both digital preservation and digital security. This finding underscores the critical need to enhance readiness factors—including infrastructure development, funding allocation, and staff capacity building—to facilitate successful AI adoption. In conclusion, AI holds immense promise to transform data preservation and security practices in academic libraries in Lagos State. However, realising this potential requires a deliberate, strategic approach that addresses both technological and human capacity limitations. To fully harness the benefits of AI, academic libraries must invest in robust infrastructure, develop staff competencies through ongoing professional development, establish clear and comprehensive policies, and secure sustainable funding mechanisms. Absent these interventions, the transformative potential of AI in safeguarding library resources will remain largely unrealised.

Recommendations:

1. Since institutional readiness was found to significantly influence AI adoption for both digital preservation and security, libraries should increase funding allocations for AI-powered systems, with dedicated budget lines for software, hardware, and maintenance.
2. The government should also upgrade technological infrastructure (servers, storage systems, and network bandwidth) to ensure compatibility with AI solutions.
3. The library leadership establish continuous professional development programs in AI tools for digital preservation and security, including practical, hands-on workshops.
4. The library leadership should advocate for localised AI solutions that address unique challenges such as unreliable power supply, internet costs, and African language processing.

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